

1 THE SIGNIFICANCE OF MONOCYTE CCR2-CCL2 AXIS IN 2 TRIPLE NEGATIVE BREAST CANCER

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28 29 **ABSTRACT**

30 *Background:* The monocyte CCR2-CCL2 axis appears to play a crucial role in forming tumor-
31 associated macrophages (TAMs), which subsequently promotes tumor metastasis and
32 resistance to therapy.

33 *Aims:* Therefore, our study assessed the monocyte CCR2-CCL2 axis in triple-negative breast
34 cancer (TNBC) and its ability to predict tumor response to neoadjuvant chemotherapy (NAC).

35 *Methods:* A study included forty-two female patients diagnosed with TNBC and qualified for
36 NAC. Responses to neoadjuvant chemotherapy were based on the pathological complete
37 response (pCR). Surface expression of CCR2 on monocytes was evaluated by flow cytometry.
38 Circulating CCL2 was measured by Luminex X-Map technology.

39 *Results:* Increased monocyte CCR2 expression and higher circulating CCL2 levels were
40 observed in the entire group of TNBC patients. After dividing the patients according to their
41 response to NAC, a significant difference was only found in the CCL2 concentration between
42 patients who achieved and did not achieve pCR. ROC curves showed that the optimum
43 diagnostic cut-off value of $CCL2 \leq 89.61$ pg/mL better discriminates TNBC patients who
44 achieved pCR than the Ki-67 index. Univariate analysis demonstrated that circulating
45 $CCL2 \leq 89.61$ pg/mL was significantly associated with pCR. However, in the multivariate
46 model, this correlation lost statistical significance.

47 *Conclusions:* Our study demonstrated the activation of the monocyte CCR2-CCL2 axis in
48 TNBC for the first time. This activation occurs mainly in patients who do not respond to NAC.
49 Circulating CCL2 levels ≤ 89.61 pg/mL were found to predict, to some extent, the achievement
50 of pCR in TNBC patients receiving NAC.

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52 Key words: Triple negative breast cancer; monocyte; CCR2-CCL2 axis; pathological
53 complete response; neoadjuvant chemotherapy

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70 INTRODUCTION

71 Triple-negative breast cancer (TNBC) accounts for approximately 15%-20% of all breast
72 cancers and is associated with high recurrence and poor overall survival (1,2). TNBC is defined
73 by the lack of expression of the estrogen receptor (ER), the progesterone receptor (PgR), and
74 the absence of human epidermal growth factor receptor 2 (HER2) overexpression based on
75 immunohistochemical staining (3,4). Patients with TNBC cannot benefit from endocrine or
76 HER2-targeted therapy, and currently, chemotherapy is the most-used therapeutic option.
77 Neoadjuvant chemotherapy (NAC), including anthracycline and taxanes, with immunotherapy,
78 in some cases, is the preferred treatment choice for patients with early and advanced stages of
79 TNBC (5). Responses to neoadjuvant chemotherapy is based on the pathological complete
80 response (pCR), indicating the absence of detectable cancer cells in the breast and lymph nodes
81 after NAC. Attaining pCR predicts benefit from further systemic oncological treatment and
82 improved overall survival (6,7). However, pCR is achieved only in 30%-65% of patients with
83 early-stage TNBC after NAC (8). Although neoadjuvant treatment increases the survival rate
84 of patients with TNBC, it also causes side effects of varying severity and affects multiple organ
85 systems (9,10). Due to the increased toxicities associated with NAC, it is essential to identify
86 patients who are most likely to benefit from this treatment without exposing everyone to the
87 potential side effects. Reliable indicators of NAC efficacy would not only avoid unnecessary
88 toxicity but also improve the prognosis of those patients who are unlikely to achieve pCR by
89 using a personalized treatment regimen or innovative therapies. Standard clinicopathological
90 characteristics at baseline, including tumor size, histologic grade, and lymph node involvement,
91 appear insufficient in predicting response to NAC. Therefore, attention is increasingly focused
92 on the tumor microenvironment (TME), being recognized as a crucial regulator of
93 carcinogenesis as well as immune evasion (11–13).

94 The TME includes a wide range of cells, such as tumor, immune, stromal, and epithelial cells,
95 that communicate with each other by secreting various cytokines and growth factors (14). The
96 effect of this cross-talk within TME may be the suppression of the immune response
97 towards cancer cells, which may result in neoplastic progression and in the acquisition of
98 resistance to anticancer therapy (15,16). In particular, tumor-associated macrophages (TAMs)
99 are a predominant myeloid population in the TME and have been implicated in avoiding
100 immune detection and metastatic dissemination in various solid tumors (17,18). TAMs
101 originate mainly from bone marrow-derived monocytes recruited to the TME by the CCL2
102 chemokine, produced by tumor cells. In some studies, elevated levels of CCL2 in breast cancer

103 biopsies correlated with increased TAM accumulation, more extensive tumor vascularization,
104 and more aggressive clinical behavior (19,20). CCL2 can stimulate the infiltration of peripheral
105 monocytes into TME by binding to the CC-chemokine receptor 2 (CCR2) expressed on their
106 surface (21). So far, the CCR2-CCL2 axis has been considered a therapeutic target in
107 developing more effective therapies based on blocking the CCR2 receptor (22). Since this axis
108 guarantees the tumor to achieve immunosuppressive properties, its importance in predicting the
109 clinical outcome of cancer patients has recently been more frequently discussed (23–25). Most
110 often, the expression of CCL2 and CCR2 was analyzed in the tumor samples, reflecting the
111 number of infiltrating TAMs. Some findings indicate that dual overexpression of CCL2/CCR2
112 in cancer biopsies is remarkably correlated with shortened survival time and increased risk of
113 recurrence (23,26,27). In human breast cancer, the level of CCL2, produced by monocytic and
114 tumor cells, was associated significantly with TAMs accumulation and was a significant
115 indicator of early relapse (20) and vessel invasion of tumor cells (28). Despite recognizing
116 TAMs as a promising target for cancer treatment, mechanisms underlying their infiltration
117 remain unknown. Activation of the monocyte CCR2-CCL2 axis seems to be one of the critical
118 steps that precede TAMs formation in TME. However, this issue has not attracted much
119 attention in the literature, neither in the context of the influence of monocyte CCR2-CCL2 axis
120 on cancer development nor its use for predictive purposes. Confirmation of its predictive
121 potential could replace the process of labeling TAMs in invasively collected biopsies with
122 assays performed in easily accessible patient blood.

123 Hence, in our preliminary study, we decided to undertake the effort to determine both the
124 expression of CCR2 on peripheral monocytes and the level of circulating CCL2 in the blood of
125 patients with TNBC. We compared the obtained results with those of healthy women and
126 patients suffering from other molecular subtypes of cancer to find out whether the activation of
127 the CCR2-CCL2 axis occurs only in TNBC or may be a common mechanism in breast cancers.
128 In addition, we assessed whether monocyte CCR2-CCL2 axis shows potential in predicting the
129 response to NAC in TNBC patients.

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131 **MATERIAL AND METHODS**

132 **Patients**

133 A study included forty-two female patients (aged 32–72 years) diagnosed with triple-negative
134 breast cancer (TNBC) who were admitted to the Greater Poland Cancer Center in Poznan

135 between October 2022 and December 2023 and were qualified for NAC. Each patient's
136 clinicopathological and relevant demographic data were documented in the breast cancer
137 database. Molecular classification of the tumors before NAC was determined using
138 immunohistochemistry-based analysis of steroid receptors, HER-2 expression and Ki-67
139 nuclear protein in tissue samples from core needle biopsy. The staging examinations before
140 NAC were based on the tumor, node, metastasis (TNM) classification according to the
141 American Joint Committee on Cancer (AJCC) 8th Edition (29). TNBC was defined as ER-
142 negative (expression in < 1% of the cancer cells), PgR negative (expression in < 1% of the
143 cancer cells), and HER-2 negative (0 or 1+ or 2+ with a negative fluorescence in situ
144 hybridization test).. The study used two reference groups: healthy blood donors of Regional
145 Blood Centre in Poznan ($n=30$) with no history of any disease and not taking any medications,
146 and women with B luminal HER-2 negative breast cancer (LBHN) qualified for NAC ($n=18$).
147 LBHN was defined as ER-positive and HER-2 negative with $Ki-67 \geq 20\%$ or/and $PgR < 20\%$.
148 Exclusion criteria for all participants were diabetes mellitus, chronic kidney disease (estimated
149 glomerular filtration rate < 60 mL/min/1.73m²), autoimmune diseases, use of contraceptives
150 and hormone replacement therapy, pregnancy, previous history of any cancer or recurrent breast
151 cancer in the last five years. Baseline clinicopathological characteristics of enrolled TNBC and
152 LBHN patients and the NAC regimen used in each cohort were summarized in Table 1.

153 All TNBC patients received taxane-based three drugs NAC, including anthracycline plus a
154 cyclophosphamide every 2 to 3 weeks for four cycles, followed by a taxane every three to four
155 cycles (AC-T). Additionally, pembrolizumab plus neoadjuvant chemotherapy was used in
156 TNBC patients with PD-L1-positive tumor cells. Of forty-two TNBC patients enrolled for the
157 study, only thirty-six completed planned cycles. The remaining patients were advised
158 discontinuation because of worsening performance status. Following NAC, patients received
159 mastectomy or breast-conserving surgery to remove the primary tumor and axillary lymph node
160 dissection to remove lymph nodes. The pathological response to NAC was assessed in the
161 surgical specimen and determined with respect to Miller-Payne grading systems (30) and
162 residual cancer burden (RCB) (31). On this basis, TNBC patients were divided into those who
163 achieved a pathological complete response (pCR group) and those who did not (non-pCR
164 group). pCR was defined as the complete disappearance of invasive cancer in the breast and the
165 absence of tumors in the axillary lymph nodes after NAC. Routine laboratory test results such
166 as complete blood count and hsCRP concentration were recorded before NAC and used to
167 compare the pCR and non-pCR groups. The study was performed in accordance with the

168 principles of the Declaration of Helsinki, and the investigational protocol was approved by the
169 Local Bioethical Committee of Poznan University of Medical Sciences (no. 551/22). Written
170 informed consent was obtained from all participants.

171 **Sample collection**

172 Peripheral blood was collected from patients on admission to the hospital for the first cycle of
173 NAC. Samples for laboratory analysis were taken from the antecubital vein after an overnight
174 fast in the sitting position.. Two neutral vacuum tubes of blood were collected from each
175 participant into ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid (EDTA) anticoagulant. After 30 min, the first
176 EDTA test tube was centrifuged at 3.000 rpm for 15 min, and the obtained plasma was stored
177 at a temperature of -80°C until all assays were performed. The second EDTA whole blood was
178 used for cytometric analysis.

179 **Laboratory analysis**

180 **Peripheral monocyte phenotyping**

181 Monocyte immunophenotyping was performed by multicolor flow cytometry using the
182 following monoclonal antibodies: CD45 APC-H7 (clone 2D1, BD Biosciences), CD14 Alexa
183 Fluor 488 (clone MΦP9, BD Biosciences), CCR2 Alexa Fluor 647 (CD192, BD Biosciences).
184 The listed antibodies were added at the manufacturer's recommended concentration to
185 cytometer tubes containing 50 µl of peripheral blood (EDTA), gently vortexed, and then
186 incubated for 15 minutes at room temperature without light. After this time, 500 µl of lysing
187 solution (BD FACS) was added to the test samples and the unstained controls and incubated
188 for another 10 minutes. Then, after adding 3 ml of phosphate-buffered saline (PBS, Dulbecco's
189 PBS (1x) w/o Ca & Mg, w/o Phenol Red, Capricorn scientific), the samples were washed twice
190 by centrifugation at 1500 rpm for 5 minutes at room temperature. The fluorochrome stained
191 cells were resuspended in 150 µl of PBS solution and acquired by FACS Aria flow cytometer
192 (Becton Dickinson) within 1 hour. The results were analyzed using the FACS Diva software
193 (Becton Dickinson), where the percentage of positive monocytes and mean fluorescent intensity
194 (MFI) were assessed. Samples without added antibodies (negative controls) were used to
195 determine the non-specific antibody reaction and autofluorescence background. Forward versus
196 side scatter (FSC vs SSC) gating was used to identify nucleated cells. Monocytes were defined
197 based on the positive expression of the CD45 antigens (Figure 1A). The percentage of positive
198 cells and mean fluorescence intensity (MFI) were determined for CCR2 (CD192) antigen on
199 monocytes (Figure 1B).

200 **Circulating CCL2 assay**

201 Circulating CCL2 in the plasma of patients was determined with the Human
202 Cytokine/Chemokine/Growth Factor Panel A (Cat. No. HCYTA-60K, Millipore Corporation,
203 Billerica), according to the manufacturer's instructions on the Luminex fully automated
204 analyzer (Luminex 200 system, Luminex Corporation, Austin, TX, USA). Luminex X-MAP
205 technology uses proprietary techniques to internally color-code microspheres with two
206 fluorescent dyes. Through precise concentrations of these dyes, distinctly colored bead sets of
207 magnetic microspheres can be created, each coated with a specific capture antibody. After an
208 analyte from a test sample is captured by the bead, a biotinylated detection antibody is
209 introduced. The reaction mixture is then incubated with Streptavidin-PE conjugate, the reporter
210 molecule, to complete the reaction on the surface of each microsphere. The microspheres are
211 allowed to pass rapidly through a laser that excites the internal dyes marking the microsphere
212 set. A second laser excites PE, i.e., the fluorescent dye on the reporter molecule. Finally, high-
213 speed digital signals identify each individual microsphere and quantify the result of its bioassay
214 based on fluorescent reporter signals. The assay procedure was given briefly as follows: The
215 filter plate was prewashed with 200 μ L wash buffer on a plate shaker for 10 minutes at room
216 temperature. The wash buffer was removed by vacuum, and 25 μ L of standards, controls, assay
217 buffer, matrix solution, and plasma samples were added into the appropriate wells. 25 μ L of the
218 beads were added to each well. The plate was incubated with agitation overnight (16–18h) at
219 4°C. After several washes, 25 μ L of detection antibodies were added and incubated for one hour
220 at room temperature, followed by 25 μ L streptavidin-phycoerythrin and 30min incubation.
221 Finally, 150 μ L of sheath fluid was added to each well, and the beads were resuspended for 5
222 minutes on a plate shaker. The analysis was performed on the Luminex 200™ platform
223 (Luminex Corporation). Each plasma sample was measured in duplicate.

224 **Statistical analysis**

225 The statistical analysis was conducted using GraphPad Prism software 6.07 (GraphPad
226 Software, San Diego, CA, USA; www.graphpad.com) and MedCalc 19.0.5 (MedCalc Software,
227 Ostend, Belgium). The normality of data distribution was tested using the Kolmogorov-
228 Smirnov or Shapiro-Wilk test. Non-normally distributed variables were presented as median
229 and Min-Max and analyzed using the non-parametric Mann-Whitney U test. Normally
230 distributed variables were presented as mean and standard deviation and analyzed using
231 Student's t-test. Categorical data and proportions were compared using the Chi-square test or
232 Fisher's exact test, as appropriate. Multiple group comparisons were performed by one-way

233 analysis of variance or the Kruskal-Wallis test respectively. Standard receiver operating curve
234 (ROC) analysis was performed to select the most appropriate cut-off values for CCL2 and
235 Ki-67 to stratify patients at a high probability of achieving pCR after NAC. The optimal cut-
236 off value was established by means of Youden's index. The correlation between circulating
237 CCL2 levels and clinicopathological characteristics was analyzed with Pearson's χ^2 test or
238 Fisher's exact test. Univariate and multivariate logistic regression analyses were performed to
239 identify potential predictors for pCR. The odds ratio (OD) and corresponding 95% confidence
240 intervals (CIs) were calculated for each analyzed variable. In the multivariate analysis, age,
241 BMI, hs-CRP, WBC, clinical tumor stage, clinical nodal stage, clinical grade, and type of
242 chemotherapy regimens were treated as potential confounders. $P \leq 0.05$ was considered
243 statistically significant.

244 RESULTS

245 The surface CCR2 expression on peripheral blood CD14⁺ monocytes and level of 246 circulating CCL2 in the whole group of TNBC patients.

247 The percentage of CCR2-expressing CD14⁺ monocytes did not change statistically in TNBC
248 compared to the patients with LBHN [86.65 (17.10-100) % versus 93.90 (15.40–100) %, $P=0.455$]
249 and control group [86.65 (17.10-100) %, versus 83.25 (48.10-98.40) %, $P=0.254$]
250 (Figure 2A). The MFI levels of CCR2 were statistically higher in TNBC patients compared to
251 controls [540 (189-3364) versus 423 (239-632)];, $P=0.004$] (Figure 2B). Increased MFI levels
252 of CCR2 were also noticed in patients with LBHN versus the control group [731 (74-3466)
253 versus 423 (239-632), $P=0.050$] (Figure 2B). However, there was no difference in MFI levels
254 of CCR2 between the analyzed breast cancer subtypes [540 (189-3364) versus 731 (74-3466),
255 $P=0.803$] (Figure 2B). Circulating CCL2 levels significantly increased in TNBC patients
256 compared with the control group [122±84.pg/mL versus 87±31 pg/mL, $P=0.039$] (Figure 2C),
257 whereas in LBHN patients, the rise of CCL2 did not reach statistical significance [84± 52 pg/mL
258 versus 87±31 pg/mL, $P=0.830$] (Figure 2C).

259 Comparison of hematological parameters and clinicopathological features between pCR 260 responders and non-responders.

261 Before the CCR2-CCL2 axis was analyzed in the pCR and non-PCR groups, baseline
262 hematological parameters and clinicopathological features were characterized in Table 2.
263 Statistical analysis showed that both groups did not differ in age, BMI, complete blood count,
264 and hsCRP concentration (Table 2). In both groups, tumor stage and grade, lymph node

265 involvement, and incidence of metastasis were similar (Table 2). Patients in both groups also
266 underwent a similar NAC regimen (Table 2). The groups differed only in the expression of
267 Ki-67, which was significantly higher in pCR responders (Table 2).

268 **The surface expression of CCR2 and circulating level of CCL2 in pCR responders and** 269 **non-responders.**

270 The percentage of CD14⁺ monocytes expressing CCR2 increased in both groups compared to
271 controls, but the change reached statistical significance only in non-pCR responders [94.10
272 (17.10-100) % versus 83.25 (48.10-98.40) %, $P=0.028$] (Figure 3A). The MFI levels of CCR2
273 levels showed a similar increasing trend, reaching the highest statistically significant value in
274 non-pCR responders compared to the control group [766 (189-1709) versus 423 (239-632) %,
275 $P=0.0003$] (Figure 3B). However, CCR2 expression on CD14⁺ monocytes measured either as
276 percentage or MFI was not significantly different between pCR responders and non-responders
277 [CCR2 %: 81.10 (24-100) versus 94.10 (17.10-100), $P=0.197$; CCR2 MFI: 508 (207-3364)
278 versus 766 (189-1709), $P=0.165$] (Figure 3A, Figure 3B). A statistically significant increase in
279 CCL2 concentration was observed only in the non-pCR patients compared to the control group
280 [113.9 (56.48-360.7) pg/mL versus 83.20 (36.97-153.3) pg/mL, $P=0.010$] (Figure 3C).
281 Furthermore, the increase in CCL2 in the non-pCR responders remained greater than in the pCR
282 responders [113.9 (56.48-360.7) pg/mL versus 76.74 (35.40-409.4), $P=0.034$] (Figure 3C).

283 **Determination of the optimal cut-offs for CCL2 and Ki-67 in predicting tumor recurrence** 284 **based on ROC curve analysis**

285 Further analysis focused only on parameters that differed significantly between pCR and non-
286 pCR patients. Since only CCL2 and Ki-67 met this criterion, the optimal cut-off points
287 stratifying the patients into pCR and non-pCR groups were determined for them. The area under
288 the curve (AUC) for CCL2 and Ki-67 is provided in Table 3. Based on the statistical analysis
289 of AUC for individual parameters, it was found that CCL2 differentiates the achievement of
290 pCR better than Ki-67 (Table 3). Corresponding to the point with the maximum combined
291 sensitivity and specificity on the ROC curve, the best cut-off value for CCL2 and Ki-67 were
292 89.61 pg/mL (sensitivity%: 71, specificity%: 68) and 50% (sensitivity%: 88, specificity%: 53),
293 respectively (Table 3). ROC curves for CCL2 and Ki-67 in predicting achievement of pCR are
294 shown in Figure 4. Further characterization of patients with low (≤ 89.61 pg/mL) and high
295 CCL2 (> 89.61 pg/mL) levels showed that the former were significantly younger and had

296 normal BMI and lower hs-CRP levels and WBC counts (Table 4). However, neither group
297 differed regarding clinicopathological tumor characteristics or NAC regimens used (Table 4).

298 **Determination of potential predictors for pCR using logistic regression analysis**

299 Logistic regression analysis assessed the association of established CCL2 and Ki-67 cut-off
300 values with pCR achievement (Table 5). Univariate analysis revealed that $CCL2 \leq 89.61$ pg/mL
301 and $Ki-67 > 50\%$ correlated significantly with pCR achievement in TNBC patients (Table 5).
302 Considering such confounders as age, BMI, hs-CRP concentration, and leukocyte count (Model
303 1), this correlation remained significant only for Ki-67 (Table 5). When adding
304 clinicopathological features to the model (Model 2), such as clinical tumor stage and grade,
305 clinical nodal stage, incident of metastasis, and the NAC regimen used, the correlation was no
306 longer statistically significant for both CCL2 and Ki-67 (Table 5).

307 **DISCUSSION**

308 TNBC tumors are highly aggressive and invasive, with an increased risk for the development
309 of early metastasis (32,33). Compared to patients with non-TNBC subtypes, TNBC patients
310 generally have a higher recurrence rate, which confers a shorter median survival time and higher
311 mortality rate within the first three years after diagnosis (32,34). Approximately 25% of TNBC
312 patients experience a locoregional and/or distant recurrence, the latter conferring a mortality
313 rate higher than 75% (35). The efficacy of currently approved treatment options (36–38) is
314 limited due to heterogeneity with oncogenic drivers and the development of resistance (39–42).
315 Improving treatment efficacy requires more thorough knowledge of the carcinogenesis of
316 TNBC. Therefore, numerous studies are being conducted to identify molecular targets and
317 novel targeting ligands that could be useful for managing TNBC effectively.

318 Our study focused on the CCR2-CCL2 axis, which is implicated in the initiation and
319 progression of various cancers (21,43). Early work with CCR2-deficient mice confirmed the
320 role of CCR2 in monocyte trafficking and recruitment (44). It is now known that CCR2
321 contributes to the egress of monocytes from the bone marrow and their influx into inflamed
322 tissues, where they transform into macrophages. Recent studies have shown that CCR2 also
323 attracts monocytes to tumors, especially metastatic sites, to generate TAMs (45–47). Most
324 TAMs originate from circulating monocytes, which can almost completely overcome the pre-
325 existing population of tissue-resident macrophages found in TME (47). Although the phenotype
326 of monocytes recruited to the tumor environment is not fully defined, evidence from various
327 experimental cancer models supports that TAMs are derived from $CCR2^+$ monocytes (47,48).

328 The chemokine CCL2 synthesized by tumor cells is essential for recruiting a subpopulation of
329 CCR2-expressing monocytes to TME (49). Ultimately, the population of TAMs generated by
330 the interaction between the monocytic CCR2 and its ligand-CCL2 promotes tumor expansion
331 through various mechanisms such as suppressing acquired immune responses, stimulating
332 angiogenesis, and modifying the extracellular matrix, thereby facilitating metastasis (50).

333 A growing number of studies have implicated the role of CCL2 and CCR2 in the progression
334 of breast cancer. Ueno et al. observed a significant correlation between TAMs and CCL2
335 expression in tissue samples of breast carcinoma resected surgically (20). Moreover, predictive
336 analysis revealed that high expression of CCL2 was an indicator of early relapse.
337 Immunohistochemistry of stromal elements of frozen sections of invasive ductal breast
338 carcinoma conducted by Valković et al. showed that TAMs are cells that predominantly express
339 CCL2 (51). Other authors who examined samples from patients with triple-negative
340 inflammatory breast cancer found them to be heavily infiltrated by TAM cells secreting high
341 levels of CCL2 (52). These results confirm that not only tumor but also TAMs themselves are
342 capable of synthesizing CCL2 and driving the process of attracting additional CCR2⁺
343 monocytes to the TME. Fang et al. and Brummer et al., whose aim was to understand the precise
344 impact of the CCR2/CCL2 axis on breast cancer behavior, demonstrated that CCR2/CCL2-
345 mediated pathways are involved in tumor growth, survival, and invasion (53,54). Findings
346 provided by Qian et al. revealed that inhibition of CCL2–CCR2 signaling blocks the recruitment
347 of monocytes, inhibits metastasis *in vivo*, and prolongs the survival of breast tumor-bearing
348 mice (46). These reports, especially those of Qiana et al., indicate that the neoplastic
349 overexpression of CCR2 and CCL2, which determines the invasive properties of breast cancer,
350 is probably preceded by the activation of the CCR2-CCL2 axis on monocytes. The monocytic
351 CCR2-CCL2 axis should, therefore, not be ignored in the context of breast cancer development
352 and expansion, as well as prognosis. In our research, we decided to look at the CCR2-CCL2
353 axis on monocytes of patients with TNBC, whose treatment remains extremely challenging
354 despite the discovery of new therapies.

355 In our study, we included pre-treated TNBC patients who were eligible for preoperative
356 neoadjuvant chemotherapy. In most cases, the tumor was not advanced, and the lymph nodes
357 were not infiltrated by tumor cells. Based on flow cytometry analysis, we showed that in
358 patients with TNBC, the percentage of monocytes expressing CCR2 does not change, but the
359 density of the receptor on their surface significantly increases compared to healthy individuals.
360 Moreover, we observed higher levels of circulating CCL2 in patients than in the control group.

361 These results indicate that the monocyte CCR2-CCL2 axis may be already activated in the early
362 stage of TNBC. However, the small cohort of patients enrolled in the study did not allow us to
363 determine whether CCR2 and CCL2 expression may increase with advancing tumor stage.

364 To investigate whether an active monocyte CCR2-CCL2 axis could be a common feature of
365 breast cancer, we decided to evaluate it in luminal B (HER-2 negative) breast cancer (LBHN).
366 Although LBHN represents a distinct molecular subtype, it shows biological similarities to
367 TNBC, especially in the subgroup with negative PR and high Ki-67 index (55). LBHN patients
368 representing the ER⁺PR⁻Ki67^{high} subgroup have poor survival outcomes, similar to those of
369 TNBC (55). Similar to TNBC, there is no targeted therapy for this phenotype of LBHN, and
370 resistance often occurs in response to endocrine treatment (55,56). Due to biological and
371 prognostic similarities to TNBC and therapeutic management difficulties, the monocytic
372 CCR2-CCL2 axis assessment in LBHN seemed justified. Although patients with LBHN
373 recruited to our study had more advanced disease and lymph node metastases were diagnosed
374 more frequently, monocyte CCR2 expression, reflected as a percentage and MFI, was
375 comparable to that observed in TNBC. In contrast to TNBC, circulating CCL2 levels in the
376 LBHN group were not significantly different from those in healthy individuals.

377 The number of reports on the expression pattern of CCR2 on peripheral monocytes and
378 circulating CCL2 levels in various cancers, including breast cancer, is limited. In addition, they
379 present conflicting results, probably due to variable recruitment criteria and cohort
380 characteristics in terms of molecular subtype and clinicopathological features of breast cancer.
381 Dehqanzada et al. observed an increase in CCL2 concentration in the blood of patients with
382 HER2-positive breast cancer. Elevated CCL2 concentration was also demonstrated by
383 Lubowicka et al. in ductal adenocarcinoma. Furthermore, the authors showed that the level of
384 CCL2 in this tumor increases with the advancing tumor stage (24). Opposite results were
385 obtained by Lebrecht et al., who analyzed systemic CCL2 levels in patients with breast cancer,
386 ductal carcinoma *in situ* (DCIS), benign breast lesions, and healthy women, showing no
387 differences between groups (57). In the study by Dwyer et al., breast cancer patients had higher
388 levels of CCL2, but this difference was not statistically significant compared to controls.
389 However, the authors did not specify the molecular subtype of the breast tumor nor its
390 clinicopathological characteristics (58). In contrast to other cited works, in ours, in addition to
391 CCL2, we also analyzed the expression of its receptor on patients' blood monocytes. Previously,
392 CCR2 expression on circulating monocytes was studied in other tumors but with inconsistent
393 results. Grossman et al. demonstrated that circulating CCR2⁺ monocytes are elevated in patients

394 with colorectal cancer (59). Furthermore, the percentage of CCR2⁺ monocytes in the peripheral
395 blood was associated with worse clinical outcomes. Patients surviving less than one-year
396 following colorectal cancer liver resection had significantly higher CCR2⁺ monocytes in the
397 blood compared to those surviving greater than one year (59). Cavassani et al., who analyzed
398 circulating monocytes in patients with stable and advanced prostate cancer, showed that there
399 was no difference in monocytic CCR2 expression levels between patients and healthy controls
400 (60). Similar results were obtained by Prat et al., who distinguished monocyte subsets in
401 patients with ovarian cancer and then analyzed the expression level of various markers,
402 including CCR2. Although classical, intermediate, and nonclassical monocytes showed varying
403 levels of CCR2, expression in each subset was comparable to that observed in healthy
404 individuals (61).

405 Our results, supported by previous reports, indicate that each tumor modulates the CCR2-CCL2
406 axis differently. Therefore, monocytic CCR2-CCL2 signaling should be analyzed individually
407 in a specific tumor and its subtypes. Activation of the CCR2-CCL2 axis or its absence may
408 indicate that distinct processes and signaling pathways are involved in tumorigenesis and
409 metastasis in particular types of cancers. Our study suggests that CCL2-mediated activation of
410 CCR2-expressing monocytes may be more likely to occur in TNBC than in LBHN. This
411 difference may be due to the fact that TNBC is classified as highly immunogenic and
412 characterized by numerous immune cell infiltrates (62–64). Although it is difficult to determine
413 whether CCR2-CCL2 activation precedes or is a consequence of tumor development, it is
414 crucial to know how it influences the invasive properties of TNBC, its ability to metastasize,
415 and its susceptibility to therapeutic procedures.

416 Tumor resection and mastectomy are traditional surgical procedures performed on patients with
417 TNBC, and adjuvant radiotherapy and chemotherapy are usually required after surgery (65).
418 Nowadays, however, NAC is considered the standard approach to treating TNBC, as it reduces
419 primary and metastatic tumor burden before surgical resection and increases the chance of
420 breast preservation (66). Anthracycline/taxane-containing chemotherapy regimens are widely
421 used as NAC, and approximately 40 to 50% of patients with TNBC treated with this scheme
422 achieve a pCR (67). Combinations of chemotherapy drugs with immune checkpoint inhibitors
423 are sometimes used in patients who meet the appropriate criteria to improve pCR rates (68).
424 Achieving a pCR is correlated with a good prognosis and is considered a surrogate marker for
425 measuring long-term clinical outcomes in TNBC (69,70). Unfortunately, there is a subgroup of
426 patients with TNBC that experience no or limited benefit from NAC. This chemotherapy-

427 resistant group shows highly aggressive tumor behavior with high recurrence rates and an
428 increased risk of metastases. These patients undergo multiple cycles of chemotherapy with
429 virtually no benefit, highlighting the need for predictive biomarkers to prevent unnecessary
430 toxicity and costs. In addition, knowledge of pre-treatment prognosis could enable the inclusion
431 of these chemotherapy-resistant patients in innovative treatment procedures, potentially
432 improving clinical outcomes. Standard clinicopathological features at baseline, including tumor
433 size, clinical grade, histological subtype, and lymph node involvement, appear insufficient to
434 predict response to NAC in patients with TNBC. Some studies have shown an association
435 between smaller, lower-grade, nonmetastatic tumors and pCR, whereas others have not (71–
436 73). New biomarkers at baseline that can identify good and poor responders would be crucial
437 for guiding treatment decisions in patients with TNBC and minimizing therapy toxicity.
438 Therefore, in the second part of our study, we assessed for the first time whether the monocyte
439 CCR2-CCL2 axis could be such a predictor of response to NAC in patients with TNBC.

440 Our preliminary characterization showed no significant differences in baseline demographic
441 and clinicopathological characteristics between TNBC patients who achieved and did not
442 achieve pCR after NAC. Both groups had similar tumor stage and lymph node status and were
443 subjected to similar preoperative treatment regimens. Only the Ki-67 index was significantly
444 higher in those patients who achieved pCR. Ki-67, a non-histone nuclear protein, is present in
445 the cell nucleus during all of the active phases of the cell cycle (G₁, S, G₂, and mitosis) but
446 absent in quiescent cells (G₀), which makes it a widely used biomarker of tumor proliferation
447 and a crucial element of pathological assessment (74,75). Our observations confirm previous
448 reports indicating that breast cancer with high Ki-67 expression responds better to
449 chemotherapy (76–78). However, routine use of Ki-67 as a predictor of prognosis and treatment
450 response in patients with breast cancer is not recommended because there is no clear standard
451 value classifying Ki-67 expression as high or low (71).

452 After initial characterization, we investigated whether monocyte CCR2-CCL2 axis changes
453 according to the patient's response to NAC. We reported a significantly increased percentage
454 of CCR2⁺ monocytes and receptor surface expression only in TNBC patients who did not
455 achieve pCR compared with healthy controls. However, NAC responders and non-responders
456 did not show a significant difference in CCR2 levels reflected by percentage and MFI. In
457 contrast, circulating CCL2 levels were increased in TNBC patients who did not achieve pCR
458 compared to those who achieved pCR and controls. These changes, mainly observed in non-
459 responding patients, suggest that the monocyte CCR2-CCL2 axis may contribute to drug

460 resistance in TNBC patients. The involvement of the monocyte CCR2-CCL2 axis in promoting
461 this phenomenon may be related to the formation of a population of TAMs in the TME, which
462 are known to be critical players in the therapy resistance of breast cancer (79). Many studies
463 have shown that TAMs can cause resistance to various breast cancer treatments by metabolic
464 reprogramming that promotes tumor angiogenesis (80) and by inducing immunosuppression
465 through the secretion of inflammatory cytokines and chemokines (81), as well as by inhibiting
466 T lymphocyte function (82).

467 Since only circulating CCL2 differed between the pCR and non-pCR patients, we further
468 analyzed the predictive properties of only this cytokine. We compared it with the Ki-67 index,
469 which also differed between the two groups and has been previously shown to be strongly
470 associated with pCR in patients with TNBC (83,84). ROC curve analysis revealed that patients
471 whose CCL2 level was less than or equal to 89.61 pg/mL were more likely to achieve pCR. The
472 optimal cut-off value for Ki-67 was also established using the Youden index in a cohort of
473 TNBC patients. In this case, it was shown that TNBC patients with Ki-67 expression levels
474 above 50% more often achieved pCR. However, it was found that the cut-off value established
475 for CCL2 allows patients to be divided into pCR and non-pCR groups with greater confidence
476 than the established Ki-67 threshold. Interestingly, patients with high CCL2 levels (>89.61
477 pg/mL), and therefore less likely to achieve pCR, were older and had elevated levels of
478 inflammatory markers such as hs-CRP and WBC count. This observation may support previous
479 reports indicating that systemic inflammation may impair treatment efficacy in patients with
480 breast cancer (85–87). It is known that systemic inflammation is caused not only by the tumor
481 itself but also by various external factors such as obesity. The excess weight found in patients
482 with high CCL2 levels in our study may be partially responsible for the observed inflammation
483 impacting the effect of chemotherapy. Hence, excess weight management (e.g., avoiding weight
484 gain, intentional weight loss, and weight-loss maintenance) is increasingly being discussed as
485 an essential factor in the prevention of cancer as well as its effective treatment (88,89).

486 Univariate analysis revealed that CCL2, like Ki-67, predicts pCR. Low CCL2 levels increased
487 pCR achievement almost five-fold. However, in the multivariate model (considering age, BMI,
488 hs-CRP, leukocyte count, tumor characteristics, and treatment regimen), CCL2 lost its
489 significance. This observation may indicate that some confounding factors, probably related to
490 demographic characteristics and inflammatory status, may interfere with the relationship
491 between CCL2 level and pCR. On the other hand, the association between CCL2 and pCR in
492 multivariate regression was close to statistical significance, which raises the possibility that

493 increasing the number of patients could lead to reaching this significance. In the study by Cohen
494 et al. involving patients with breast cancer, elevated serum CCL2 levels significantly shortened
495 progression-free survival and overall survival (90). The role of circulating CCL2 in predicting
496 clinical outcomes has also been demonstrated in other types of cancer. Tas et al. have shown
497 that serum levels of CCL2 may be a predictive indicator for chemoresponsivity in gastric cancer
498 patients (91). You et al. demonstrated that the low preintervention CCL2 in serum of patients
499 with hepatocellular carcinoma undergoing transarterial chemoembolization correlates with a
500 higher probability of achieving objective tumor response according to the modified Response
501 Evaluation Criteria in Solid Tumors (mRECIST) (92). Our results, confirmed by the authors of
502 the mentioned works, are consistent with previous reports showing a strong predictive potential
503 of CCL2 expression in extracts from primary tumors (93) and further suggest that the elevation
504 of circulating CCL2 may also be useful.

505 A notable limitation of our study is that it was conducted in a single center, and the sample size
506 was small. Furthermore, we did not perform a histochemical evaluation of TAMs in tumor
507 samples, making it difficult to conclude how monocyte CCR2-CCL2 axis influences their
508 formation. Because the study was conducted in a short period, we did not analyze whether
509 CCL2 could also help predict long-term clinical outcomes such as disease-free survival (DFS)
510 and overall survival (OS). These aspects require verification and should be the target of further
511 studies.

512

513 **CONCLUSIONS**

514 In conclusion, our study is the first to indicate the activation of the CCR2-CCL2 monocyte axis
515 in patients with TNBC, especially those not responding to neoadjuvant therapy. The association
516 between an active monocyte CCR2-CCL2 axis and failure to achieve pCR may suggest its
517 involvement in the phenomenon of chemoresistance, which requires further verification at the
518 molecular level. Moreover, we are the first to indicate that circulating CCL2 may be a
519 noninvasive predictor of pCR in patients with TNBC, which requires confirmation in larger
520 population studies.

521

522 **DECLARATION OF CONFLICTS OF INTEREST**

523 All authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest.

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850 TABLES

851 Table 1. Baseline demographic and clinicopathological characteristics of control individuals
852 and breast cancer patients involved in the study.

Parameter	Control (n=30)	TNBC (n = 42)	LBHN (n = 18)	p-value
Age (years)	47±8	53±13*	45±7	0.028 ^a
BMI (kg/m ²)	25±4	26±5	28±6	NS ^a
Smoking habit	1/30	3/42	3/18	NS ^b
Clinical tumor stage <i>n</i> (%)				NS ^b
cT1	-	6 (14.28)	0 (0)	
cT2	-	28 (66.66)	11 (61.11)	
cT3	-	6 (14.28)	4 (22.22)	
cT4	-	2 (4.76)	3 (16.66)	
Clinical nodal stage <i>n</i> (%)				0.005 ^b
cN0	-	28 (66.66)	4 (22.22)	
cN1	-	13 (30.95)	12 (66.66)	
cN2	-	1 (2.38)	2 (11.11)	
Distant metastasis <i>n</i> (%)				NS ^b
Present	-	3 (7.14)	1 (5.55)	
Absent	-	39 (92.95)	17 (94.44)	
Overall clinical stage <i>n</i> (%)				0.030 ^b
I	-	5 (10.41)	0 (0)	
IIA	-	22 (52.38)	3 (16.66)	
IIB	-	7 (16.66)	7 (38.88)	
IIIA	-	4 (9.52)	4 (22.22)	
IIIB	-	2 (4.76)	3 (16.66)	
IV	-	2 (4.76)	1 (5.55)	
Clinical grade <i>n</i> (%)				NS ^b
G2	-	16 (38.09)	10 (66.66)	
G3	-	26 (61.90)	8 (44.44)	
Ki-67 (%)	-	75 (10-100)	40 (20-90)	0.007 ^c
Neoadjuvant chemotherapy regimen <i>n</i> (%)				<0.001
AC-T	-	23 (54.76)	18 (100)	
AC-T + <i>pembrolizumab</i>	-	19 (45.23)	0 (0)	

853 TNBC- triple negative breast cancer; LBHN- luminal B HER2 negative breast cancer; BMI- body mass index;
854 AC-T- deoxyrubicine and cyclophosphamide plus paclitaxel/docetaxel; NS- not statistically significant.
855 ^aResults shown as mean ± standard deviation, comparison done by using one-way ANOVA test followed by the
856 Turkey's multiple comparison test. ^bCategorical data, comparison done by Fischer's exact test. ^cResults shown as

857 median and Min-Max, comparison done by using Mann-Whitney test. $P \leq 0.05$ was considered statistically
858 significant.*TNBC versus LBHN.

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869 Table 2. Comparison of demographic, hematological parameters and clinicopathological
 870 features between pCR responders and non-responders among TNBC patients.

Parameter	pCR responders (n=18)	Non-pCR responders (n=18)	p-value
Age (years)	49±12	55±14	NS ^a
BMI (kg/m ²)	25.33±4.58	27.59±5.81	NS ^a
WBC (10 ⁹ /L)	6.56±1.34	7.15±2.21	NS ^a
NEUT (10 ⁹ /L)	4.09±1.37	4.66±1.94	NS ^a
MONO (10 ⁹ /L)	0.40 (0.18-0.79)	0.39 (0.23-1.20)	NS ^b
LYMTH (10 ⁹ /L)	1.85±0.53	1.80±0.59	NS ^a
RBC (10 ¹² /L)	4.47±0.37	4.37±0.26	NS ^a
HGB (mmol/L)	13.45±0.97	12.98±0.96	NS ^a
PLT (10 ⁹ /L)	266±49	248±48	NS ^a
hsCRP (mg/L)	1.35 (0.20-13.60)	2.40 (0.20-9.50)	NS ^b
CA-15.3 (IU/mL)	20.90 (8.80-53.90)	21.30 (1.30-101)	NS ^b
Ki-67 (%)	75 (40-100)	50 (10-95)	0.018 ^b
Clinical tumor stage <i>n</i> (%)			NS ^c
cT1/cT2	16 (89)	15 (83)	
cT3/cT4	2 (11)	3 (17)	
Clinical nodal stage <i>n</i> (%)			NS ^c
cN0	14 (78)	11 (61)	
cN1/cN2	4 (22)	7 (39)	
Metastasis <i>n</i> (%)			NS ^c
Absent	17 (94)	16 (89)	
Present	1 (5)	2 (11)	
Clinical grade <i>n</i> (%)			NS ^c
G2	4 (22)	10 (55)	
G3	14 (78)	8 (44)	
Neoadjuvant chemotherapy regimen <i>n</i> (%)			NS ^c
AC-T	8 (44)	14 (77)	
AC-T + pembrolizumab	10 (56)	4 (22)	

871 BMI- body mass index; WBC- white blood cells; NEUT- neutrophils; MONO- monocytes; LYMTH-
 872 lymphocytes; RBC- red blood cells; HGB-hemoglobin; PLT- blood platelets; hsCRP- highly sensitive C-reactive
 873 protein; AC-T- deoxyrubicine and cyclophosphamide plus paclitaxel/docetaxel; NS- not statistically significant.
 874 ^aResults shown as mean ± standard deviation, comparison done by using unpaired *t*-test. ^bResults shown as median
 875 and Min-Max, comparison done by using Mann-Whitney test. ^cCategorical data, comparison done by Fischer's
 876 exact test. *P*≤0.05 was considered statistically significant.

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881 Table 3. Receiver operating characteristic (ROC) curve analysis for the optimal cut-off values
882 of CCL2 and Ki-67 in predicting pCR to NAC.

Parameter	AUC	95% CI	Cut-off value	<i>p</i>-value
CCL2 (pg/mL)	0.693	0.518 – 0.836	89.61	0.031
Ki-67 (%)	0.667	0.491 – 0.815	50	0.070

883 The optimal cutoff value was established by means of Youden's index. AUC- area under the curve; 95% CI- 95%
884 confidence interval. $P \leq 0.05$ was considered statistically significant.

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910 Table 4. Comparison between TNBC patients categorized according to pre-treatment CCL2
 911 cut-off value.

Parameter	CCL2≤89.61 pg/mL (n=17)	CCL2>89.61 pg/mL (n=19)	p-value
Age (years)	47±12	57±13	0.028 ^a
BMI (kg/m ²)	23.32±4.29	29.36±4.40	<0.001 ^a
WBC (10 ⁹ /L)	6.22±1.43	7.42±1.99	0.047 ^a
hsCRP (mg/L)	0.80 (0.20-6.40)	2.50 (0.50-13.60)	0.014 ^b
Ki-67 (%)	75 (30-100)	70 (10-95)	NS ^b
Clinical tumor stage <i>n</i> (%)			NS ^c
cT1/cT2	15 (88)	16 (84)	
cT3/cT4	2 (12)	3 (16)	
Clinical nodal stage <i>n</i> (%)			NS ^c
cN0	13 (76)	13 (68)	
cN1/cN2	4 (24)	6 (32)	
Metastasis <i>n</i> (%)			NS ^c
Absent	16 (94)	17 (89)	
Present	1 (6)	2 (11)	
Clinical grade <i>n</i> (%)			NS ^c
G2	5 (29)	9 (47)	
G3	13 (71)	10 (53)	
Neoadjuvant chemotherapy regimen <i>n</i> (%)			NS ^c
AC-T	9 (53)	13 (68)	
AC-T + <i>pembrolizumab</i>	8 (47)	6 (32)	

912 BMI- body mass index; WBC– white blood cells; hsCRP- highly sensitive C-reactive protein; AC-T-
 913 deoxyrubicine and cyclophosphamide plus paclitaxel/docetaxel; NS- not statistically significant. ^aResults shown
 914 as mean ± standard deviation, comparison done by using unpaired *t*-test. ^bResults shown as median and Min-Max,
 915 comparison done by using Mann-Whitney test. ^cCategorical data, comparison done by Fischer`s exact test. *P*≤0.05
 916 was considered statistically significant.

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Table 5. Univariate and multivariate logistic regression analysis of association between estimated CCL2 and Ki-67 cutoff values and pCR after NAC in TNBC patients.

Variables	Univariate				Multivariate							
					Model 1 ^a				Model 2 ^b			
	β	OR	95% CI	<i>P</i>	β	OR	95% CI	<i>P</i>	β	OR	95% CI	<i>P</i>
CCL2 \leq 89.61 pg/mL	1.569	4.80	1.15 – 20.08	0.032	1.852	6.37	0.74 – 54.56	0.091	2.029	7.61	0.69 – 84.06	0.098
Ki-67 > 50%	2.014	7.50	1.31 – 42.77	0.023	2.474	11.87	1.41 – 99.79	0.022	2.466	11.78	0.96 – 143.61	0.053

Bolded *P* value indicates statistical significance. OR – odds ratio; 95% CI - 95% confidence interval. ^aModel 1 adjusted for age, BMI, hsCRP, and WBC. ^bModel 2 adjusted for age, BMI, hsCRP, WBC, clinical tumor stage, clinical nodal stage, clinical grade, incidence of metastasis, therapy regimen. $P \leq 0.05$ was considered statistically significant.

FIGURES DESCRIPTIONS

Figure 1. Representative flow cytometry diagram of the gating strategy for CCR2 expressing monocytes. A. Dot plots for representative flow cytometry gating for monocyte populations based on FSC, SSC parameters, and CD45⁺/CD14⁺ expression. B. Dot plots represent the flow cytometry analysis of CCR2 on monocyte population (% of positive cells), and histograms compare the parameters in healthy donors and TNBC patients.

Figure 2. Assessment of the CCR2-CCL2 axis in TNBC compared with LBHN and controls. CCR2 expression on CD14⁺ monocytes measured as the percentage (A) or MFI (B) in two types of breast cancer and controls. Results are presented as the median and Min-Max and analyzed using the Kruskal–Wallis test with Dunn’s multiple comparisons. C. Concentration of circulating CCL2 in two types of breast cancer and controls. Results are shown as mean±SD and analyzed using ANOVA test with Turkey’s multiple comparisons. * $p\leq 0.05$; ** $p<0.01$; ns- nonsignificant.

Figure 3. Comparison of the CCR2-CCL2 axis between pCR responders and non-responders among TNBC patients. CCR2 expression on CD14⁺ monocytes measured as the percentage (A) or MFI (B) in the pCR and non-pCR groups and controls. Results are presented as the median and Min-Max and analyzed using the Kruskal–Wallis test with Dunn’s multiple comparisons. C. Concentration of circulating CCL2 in in the pCR and non-pCR groups and controls. Results are presented as the median and Min-Max and analyzed using the Kruskal–Wallis test with Dunn’s multiple comparisons. * $p\leq 0.05$; ** $p<0.001$; ns- nonsignificant.

Figure 4. ROC curves for CCL2 and Ki-67 as predictors for pCR. Black dots indicate estimated cutoffs that most accurately predict pCR in patients with TNBC. The optimal cut-off value was established by means of Youden’s index.

Figure 1.

Figure 2

Figure 3

Figure 4

